

Macrophagic Myofasciitis in a Genetically Susceptible Individual: A Case Report Linking Aluminum Adjuvants, Iron Overload, and Variants in TFR2 and SLC40A1

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Abstract

We report the case of a woman born in 1970, diagnosed with macrophagic myofasciitis (MMF) following adverse reactions to aluminum-containing vaccines throughout her life. Genetic testing revealed heterozygosity for the HFE C282Y variant, multiple homozygous polymorphisms in TFR2, and heterozygous mutations in SLC40A1, suggesting a possible predisposition to altered iron metabolism. Despite normal iron levels in earlier years, mild iron overload and intermittent liver enzyme elevations were observed after menopause, despite regular blood donations. This case raises the question of whether genetic variants affecting iron regulation could also modulate aluminum retention and contribute to MMF pathophysiology.

Keywords:

Case report, Macrophagic Myofasciitis, Aluminum adjuvants, Ferroportin mutations, TFR2 polymorphisms, Iron overload, Post-vaccine reactions, Genetic susceptibility, Heparin regulation, Liver involvement, Environmental metals, Personalized medicine.

Background

Macrophagic myofasciitis (MMF) is a rare inflammatory muscle disease associated with long-term persistence of aluminum-based vaccine adjuvants in macrophages. Although MMF is linked to aluminum exposure, genetic factors modulating iron metabolism might influence individual susceptibility to aluminum retention and toxicity. We report a complex case highlighting the possible interplay between MMF, iron overload, and genetic polymorphisms in iron-handling genes, suggesting broader implications for understanding metal metabolism in chronic inflammatory diseases.

Case Presentation

Demographics and Early Medical History

A woman born in 1970, of predominantly Irish and Anglo-Saxon ancestry (98.7% according to genetic analysis), presented early signs of aluminum intolerance following vaccination. At the age of one year, after a Vaxicoq vaccine injection near the scapula, a hollow at the

36 injection site developed, suggestive of localized tissue necrosis. The sterile wound remained
37 open for several months, and the scar is still visible more than 50 years later.

38 Throughout her childhood, she experienced recurrent infections (otitis), muscle pain, fatigue,
39 sleep disturbances, emotional dysregulation, learning difficulties, digestive disorders, and
40 restless legs syndrome. Her mother consistently noted poor tolerance to vaccinations.

41 Major Clinical Events

42 • **1996–1997:** Following three doses of the Genhevac B hepatitis B vaccine, she
43 developed new symptoms: chronic fatigue, muscle tetany, cognitive impairment,
44 arthralgias, sleep disturbances, and mood instability. This vaccination marked the
45 onset of progressive physical and cognitive decline.

46 • **2010:** After a DTPolio (Repevax) vaccine, her health deteriorated further, with the
47 development of a goiter, erythema nodosum, digestive disturbances, and recurrent
48 otitis. Another hollow formed at the injection site in the left deltoid. Later, a
49 subsequent muscle biopsy diagnosed macrophagic myofasciitis (MMF).

50 Management and Evolution

51 In 2012, iron supplementation with lithothamnion was attempted to address iron deficiency
52 but was discontinued due to a metallic body odor and concerns regarding aluminum
53 intoxication.

54 In 2013, Dupuytren's disease appeared following the removal of dental amalgams. Although
55 studies have not firmly linked Dupuytren's disease to hemochromatosis, a higher prevalence
56 among Celtic-descendant populations suggests a potential genetic/environmental overlap. [[1](#),
57 [2](#)]

58 In 2017, the patient was diagnosed with Asperger's syndrome with mood disorder, revising
59 the previous diagnosis of bipolar disorder.

60 Starting in 2013, she began donating blood regularly while maintaining normal iron levels
61 without supplementation. However, after menopause in 2019, laboratory iron markers began
62 to indicate mild overload despite continued blood donations. Liver enzyme levels were also
63 intermittently elevated, correlating with periods of increased iron stores. Both iron levels and
64 liver enzymes tended to normalize after further blood donations.

65 Iron parameters and liver enzyme levels were monitored regularly. Before menopause, iron
66 stores remained stable. After menopause, a progressive increase in ferritin and transferrin
67 saturation was observed, accompanied by slight elevations of liver enzymes, despite regular
68 blood donations.

69 Summary of Abnormal Iron and Liver Parameters

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Blood test date	Ferritin (ng/mL)	Transferrin Saturation (%)	AST (IU/L)	ALT (IU/L)	GGT (IU/L)	Comment
December 2023	298	59%	34	126	146	Iron overload and high liver enzymes
October 2022	189	48%	26	38	83	Elevated transferrin saturation and GGT
January 2021	109	38%	34	93	79	Elevated ALAT - GGT
February 2020	106.3	35%				Transferrin saturation just at the limit
March 2016	59.6	28%	19	33	24	Normal iron and liver enzymes

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73 **TIBC:** Total iron-binding capacity

74 **Normal reference ranges:**

- 75 • Ferritin: 15-150 ng/mL
- 76 • Transferrin saturation: 20-45%
- 77 • ALAT: <35 U/L
- 78 • ASAT: <35 U/L
- 79 • GGT: <40 U/L

80 **Observation:** Progressive increase in ferritin and transferrin saturation post-menopause,
81 associated with mild elevation of liver enzymes despite regular blood donations.

82 Genetic Testing Results

83 Table summarizing genetic variants and frequencies

Gene	Variant (rsID)	Genotype	Allele Frequencies (Ref/Alt)
HFE	rs1800562 (C282Y)	Heterozygous (A/G)	C : 0.95 / A : 0.05
TFR2	rs4729598	Homozygous (T/T)	C : 0.88 / T : 0.12
TFR2	rs4727457	Homozygous (T/T)	C : 0.84 / T : 0.16
TFR2	rs4729600	Homozygous (T/T)	C : 0.84 / T : 0.16
TFR2	rs7385804	Homozygous (C/C)	A : 0.63 / C : 0.37
SLC40A1	rs4667287	Heterozygous (A/C)	A : 0.89 / C : 0.10
SLC40A1	rs7596205	Heterozygous (A/G)	G : 0.89 / A : 0.10

84

85 SLC40A1 gene, associated with ferroportin disease is an autosomal dominant condition.

86 Several studies have investigated the functional impact of genetic variants in HFE, TFR2, and
87 SLC40A1 genes on iron homeostasis. While some variants (e.g., HFE C282Y) are well
88 established in hereditary hemochromatosis, the contribution of other polymorphisms remains
89 under active investigation. Below are selected references highlighting associations between

90 these variants and iron-related metabolic disorders or chronic inflammatory conditions. [[3](#), [4](#), [5](#),
91 [6](#), [7](#), [8](#), [9](#), [10](#), [11](#), [12](#), [13](#)]

92

93 Discussion

94 This case illustrates a complex interaction between environmental aluminum exposure,
95 genetic predisposition to iron metabolism disorders, and chronic inflammatory responses.
96 The early and recurrent reactions to aluminum-containing vaccines, together with
97 macrophagic myofasciitis confirmed by muscle biopsy, support a diagnosis of aluminum
98 intolerance.

99 The development of mild iron overload post-menopause, despite regular blood donations,
100 raises concern for underlying dysregulation of iron homeostasis.
101 Notably, the presence of multiple variants in TFR2 and SLC40A1 may have disrupted
102 hepcidin regulation and ferroportin function, favoring iron accumulation in macrophages and
103 liver cells.

104 Moreover, the coexistence of Dupuytren's disease and MMF — both associated with HLA-
105 DRB1 alleles — suggests a possible shared autoimmune or inflammatory pathway
106 exacerbated by metal dysregulation. [[14](#), [15](#)]

107 This case strengthens the hypothesis that genetic polymorphisms affecting iron metabolism
108 may also modulate the body's handling of aluminum, leading to persistent inflammatory
109 sequelae in susceptible individuals.

110 Further studies investigating the role of ferroportin, TFR2 dysfunction, and metal retention in
111 MMF and other chronic inflammatory diseases are warranted.

112

113 For a detailed review of iron metabolism, hereditary hemochromatosis, and their possible role
114 in macrophagic myofasciitis, see:
115 Gwénola Le Dref (2025). Iron metabolism, hereditary hemochromatosis and aluminum:
116 pathogenic links in macrophage myofasciitis Review. Preprint available on Zenodo.
117 [10.5281/zenodo.15315722](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15315722)

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119 Conclusion

120 This case highlights the potential synergistic role of genetic variants in iron metabolism and
121 environmental aluminum exposure in the pathogenesis of macrophagic myofasciitis.
122 Personalized assessment of genetic susceptibility could help inform individualized risk
123 assessment and guide safer vaccine adjuvant choices in the future.

124 Conflict of Interest Statement

125 The author declares no financial or institutional conflict of interest. However, she has been
126 diagnosed with macrophagic myofasciitis (MMF), which motivated her interest in this topic.

127 This personal context did not influence the interpretation of scientific data presented in this
128 work.

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